

Pretreatment with Tualang Honey Improves Brain Anti-Oxidant/Oxidant Status of Rats Exposed to Normobaric Hypoxia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tualang honey has been shown to reduce oxidative stress in various animal models.

Objective: This study aims to investigate the responses of antioxidant defenses to normobaric hypoxia and the effects of Tualang honey on brain oxidant/antioxidant status of adult male rats.

Methods: The rats were divided into four groups (n = 12 per group); i) sucrose non-hypoxia, ii) sucrose with hypoxia, iii) honey non-hypoxia, iv) honey with hypoxia. Oral Tualang honey (0.2 g/kg body weight) and sucrose (1 mL of 7.9%) supplementations were given to the rats daily for 14 days. The rats were then subjected to ~11% continuous normobaric hypoxia for 7 days. The brain homogenate was used to determine oxidative stress markers levels/activities.

Results: The sucrose with hypoxia group demonstrated a significant increase in malondialdehyde (MDA) and a decrease in total antioxidant capacity (TAC), catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) levels when compared to sucrose non-hypoxia group. A significant increase in TAC, CAT, SOD and GPx, and a decrease in MDA levels were observed especially in honey with hypoxia group compared to sucrose with hypoxia group.

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that normobaric hypoxia disrupts the efficiency of the antioxidant system leading to oxidative damage. Pretreatment with Tualang honey has been demonstrated to increase brain tolerance to hypoxia.

KEY WORDS

hypoxia, Tualang honey, sucrose, brain, oxidative stress

INTRODUCTION

Stress is one of the basic etiologies of many diseases¹⁾. It can be produced by psychological, physiological, or environmental stressors such as cold, heat, hypoxia, physical exercise or malnutrition^{2,3)}. Hypoxia and ischemia are associated with increased release of glutamate⁴⁾ as well as with increased oxygen radical production and membrane lipid peroxidation⁴⁻⁸⁾.

Two possible mechanisms have been put forward to explain how hypoxia induces oxidative stress⁹⁾. One of the mechanisms is related to the mitochondrial electron transport chain in respiration, in which the electron carriers in the electron transport chain are reduced under

hypoxia, allowing more electrons to escape from the chain and react with oxygen molecules¹⁰⁻¹²⁾. The second mechanism involves the xanthine reductase/xanthine oxidase system. Theoretically, xanthine reductase under low oxygen availability can be converted to its oxidase form via the limitation of proteolysis or oxidation, with the subsequent increase in O₂⁻ and H₂O₂ production^{12,13)}. The abundant reactive oxygen species (ROS) can oxidize phospholipids in the membrane, damage the cell membrane and cause pathological conditions^{14,15)}, especially to the brain.

The brain is sensitive to oxidative damage for a number of reasons¹⁶⁾. It consumes a considerable amount of oxygen and therefore produces a comparatively large amount of free radical by-products while having relatively modest antioxidant defenses. In addition, the brain is

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Figure 1. Effects of Tualang honey pretreatment on brain oxidant/antioxidant levels. Values are shown as means \pm S.E.M. * $P < 0.05$ denotes significantly different between non-hypoxia and hypoxia groups. # $P < 0.05$ denotes significantly different between sucrose with hypoxia and honey with hypoxia groups.

rich in lipid substrates for oxidation, as well as iron and copper ions that catalyse free radical reactions⁽⁶⁾.

The beneficial effects of dietary antioxidants including honey as a therapeutic or preventive approach to many diseases have been widely published. Malaysian Tualang honey has been reported to possess the highest antiradical activity compared to Gelam honey, Indian forest honey and Pineapple honey⁽¹⁷⁾. It has been shown to reduce oxidative stress in animals⁽¹⁸⁻²¹⁾ as well as in human⁽²²⁾. We have recently published the role of antioxidant in hypoxia-induced learning and memory deficit⁽²³⁾. In the present study, we aimed to investigate the responses of antioxidant defenses to normobaric hypoxia in male rats. This finding may serve as a reference to evaluate the effects of Tualang honey pretreatment on brain oxidant/antioxidant system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals

Forty-eight adult male Sprague-Dawley rats at approximately 8-weeks old, with a body weight of 200 ± 20 g, were obtained from the Laboratory Animal Research Unit, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM). All rats were housed in polypropylene cages (32 x 24 x 16 cm), exposed to 12-hour light-dark cycles, maintained at a room temperature of 23°C, and had free access to food and water. The experimental protocol was approved by the Research and Ethics Committee, USM. The protocol was approved by the ethics committee (USM/Animal Ethics Approval/2015/(95)(609)) of this university, in accordance with the internationally accepted principles for laboratory animal use and care.

The rats were randomly divided into four groups ($n = 12$ per group); i) sucrose non-hypoxia, ii) sucrose with hypoxia, iii) honey non-hypoxia, iv) honey with hypoxia. The rats were orally fed with either 1 mL of 0.2 g/kg body weight Tualang honey⁽²⁴⁾ or 7.9% sucrose⁽²⁵⁾ supplementa-

tions daily for 14 days. The environmental hypoxia at an O₂ content of ~11% was generated by the HCA HYPO-002 high-altitude simulation system. The rats were placed in the acrylic air-tight chamber with constant temperature (~25°C) and humidity (~76%) continuously for 7 days. The rats' food intake and body weight change were recorded weekly.

Blood collection

The animals were sacrificed by decapitation immediately after the behavioural test. A total of 10 ml of blood was collected immediately via cardiac puncture. All blood samples were left to clot for 2 hours prior to centrifugation for 15 min at 4000 rpm (EBA 21, Hettich GmbH & Co. KG, Tuttlingen, Germany). Approximately 3 ml of serum was collected and stored at -20°C until assay.

Estimation of serum corticosterone level

Serum corticosterone level was measured using a specific ELISA kit (Abcam Corticosterone ELISA kit; Cambridge, MA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 25 µL of corticosterone standards and samples were added to each well followed by 25 µL of biotinylated corticosterone protein. The plate was incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. Following incubation, the wells were washed with 200 µL wash buffer 5 times and 50 µL of 1 x SP conjugate added to each well and then incubated for 30 min. Following five washes, 50 µL of chromogen substrate was added to each well and incubated for 20 min. Next, 50 µL of stop solution was added into each well. The absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. Waltham, MA, USA).

Preparation of brain homogenate

Brains from each group were quickly removed and carefully dissected in ice-cold saline to separate the brain hemispheres. The isolated

hemispheres were then weighed and a homogenate (10% w/v) was prepared from the left hemisphere in ice-cold 0.1M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) whereas the right hemisphere was kept for histological study. The homogenates were then centrifuged with speed centrifugation (10,000 x g) for 10 min. The samples were kept at -80°C until assay.

Assay of oxidative stress biomarkers

The levels of total antioxidant capacity (TAC), superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and malondialdehyde (MDA) in the brain homogenate were also measured using a specific ELISA kit (BioAssay Systems, Hayward, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocols.

Statistical analysis

Values of outcome data are expressed as mean + standard error of the mean (SEM). The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Bonferroni post-hoc tests were used to examine the mean differences between the experimental groups. A probability value of < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant difference.

RESULTS

Serum corticosterone level

The serum corticosterone levels were highest in the sucrose with hypoxia group, followed by the honey with hypoxia, sucrose non-hypoxia, and honey non-hypoxia groups.

Levels of oxidative stress biomarkers in the brain homogenate

A one-way ANOVA data showed a significant difference among the experimental groups in the mean levels of SOD [F (3, 47) = 7.69; $P < 0.05$], CAT [F (3, 47) = 37.83; $P < 0.05$], GPx [F (3, 47) = 12.16; $P < 0.05$], TAC [F (3, 47) = 10.99; $P < 0.05$], and MDA [(3, 47) = 7.64; $P < 0.05$] of the brain homogenate as shown in the Figure 1.

Post hoc analysis showed that the mean levels of SOD, CAT, GPx and TAC were significantly lower in the sucrose with hypoxia group compared to the other experimental groups. Their mean levels in honey with hypoxia was comparable to both honey and sucrose non-hypoxia groups.

For the mean level of MDA, post hoc analysis showed that the level was significantly higher in the sucrose with hypoxia group compared to the other experimental groups. The mean level of MDA in honey with hypoxia was comparable to both honey and sucrose non-hypoxia groups.

DISCUSSION

Finding of this study indicated Tualang honey could reduce the stress due to hypoxia exposure as shown by the lower corticosterone level in hypoxia with honey group which were comparable to that of non-hypoxia controls. These results were supported by findings from previous studies in ovariectomized rats exposed to social stress²⁴, young and aged rats exposed to noise stress²⁶, and rats exposed to restraints and swim stress²⁷. The occurrence of oxidative stress and depletion of the antioxidant defenses have been invariably associated with hypoxic stress in human as well as in animal^{8,28-32} and these findings were consistent with our results.

MDA is one of the final products of lipid peroxidation in the cell membrane. The MDA level, which can reflect the degree of cell oxidative damage, is generally used as a sensitive indicator to evaluate the level of lipid peroxidation. In the present study, we found that higher MDA and lower antioxidant enzymes levels following hypoxia exposure. Higher brain lipid peroxidation was the consequence of enhanced ROS production and lower antioxidant enzyme activities. These could be possibly explained by the large amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids in the brain, which are highly susceptible to oxidative reactions³³. Free radicals especially the hydroxyl radicals (OH⁻) and H₂O₂ directly attack

the brain membrane lipids³⁴. Thus, hypoxia induced oxidative damage via peroxidation of brain membrane lipids.

These findings were in agreement with previous results on rodents^{31,32,35,36}, triploid crucian⁹ and gilthead sea bream³⁷ under hypoxia. Nonetheless, the results from other previous studies demonstrated that lipid peroxides decrease in the brain *C. carpio*³⁸ and *P. glenii*³⁹ under low oxygen conditions. These conflicting findings indicate that the oxidative damage induced by hypoxic stress was tissue- and species-specific⁹. The underlying mechanisms warrant further investigations.

The relative contribution of each antioxidant enzyme to protect against hypoxia-associated oxidative stress during periods of oxygen depletion is not well-known, and the relationships among ROS levels, oxidative stress markers, and antioxidant enzymes activities/levels are complex⁴⁰. Our study found a significant decrease in antioxidant enzymes levels following hypoxia exposure in sucrose-treated rats. The decrement is mainly attributed to their roles to scavenge free radical and protect biomolecules from free radical attack as reported in the previous study⁴¹.

Tualang honey pretreatment at a dose of 0.2 g/kg for 2 weeks significantly lowered the mean MDA level comparable to sucrose non-hypoxia group. The mean SOD, CAT, GPx and TAC levels, conversely, were higher in both Tualang honey-treated groups as in other previous studies^{26,42}. These results suggest that Tualang honey was able to upregulate antioxidant enzymes under both normoxic and hypoxic conditions in rats. The positive effect on rats brain is probably partly due to the antioxidant properties found in Tualang honey such as flavonoids (catechin, kaempferol, naringenin, luteolin and apigenin) and phenolic acids (gallic, syringic, benzoic, trans-cinnamic, p-coumaric, and caffeic acids)^{17,43,44}.

CONCLUSION

Exposure to normobaric hypoxia disrupts the efficiency of the antioxidant system. Pretreatment with Tualang honey has been demonstrated to increase levels of the antioxidant enzymes with a concomitant decrease in MDA of rat brain. Thus, Tualang honey may be used as pretreatment to increase hypoxic tolerance and prevent brain oxidative stress.

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